

ability of forming O-H bond simultaneously with electron transfer. Consequently, increasing amounts of carbinolate free radicals are formed. The latter is not reduced at its formation potential and so dimerizes until its reduction potential is reached (Fig. 2). The need of additional energy for electro-reduction of the anionic free radical arises from the coulombic repulsion between the electrode and the anion; further the electron affecting the reduction now has to enter an area of increased electron density.

Fig. 2. Reduction of a carbonyl compound in alkaline media.

The polarographic measurements were made using DME (as working electrode) and SCE (reference electrode) in 10 ml H-type polarographic cell. The M/40 solution of each carbonyl compound [1 ml carbonyl compound solution + 4 ml KCl (2.5 M) + 5 ml BR-buffer (pH 9.0)] taken in

in 2.5 M KCl (supporting electrolyte) and BR buffer (pH 9.0) at glassy carbon electrode using Ag/AgCl as reference electrode. All curves are shown in Fig. 3.

For constant potential electrolysis, the conventional three-electrode cells with stainless steel as cathode (working), platinum as counter and calomel as reference electrodes was used. All reductions were carried out under N₂ atmosphere. In each case a 1.00 M CH₃COONa was used as a supporting electrolyte. The pH of the solution was maintained constant at 9.0.

Table 1. Experimental conditions of electrolysis

Compd.	Applied potential mV	Yield %
Benzil	1610	80.10
Salicylaldehyde	1510	77.07

All of the electrolysis were carried out at their corresponding reduction potentials and were complete in 2 h (Table 1). In each case the workup involved extracting the aqueous solutions with ethyl ether (3 × 50 ml). The ether extracts were then combined and washed with aqueous saturated NaCl solution. The organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and then characterized.

The products showed characteristic IR bands at 1400–1310 and 1150 cm⁻¹ due to C–O stretching (tertiary al-

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of compounds : (A) salicylaldehyde and (B) benzil.

the cell is purged with N₂ for 10–15 min before each run. In each case a blank run of the solvent and BR-buffer were also taken to ascertain the wave due to carbonyl compound. The voltammograms of benzil and salicylaldehyde in 1 : 1 (v/v) ethanol-water at 0.5 mM concentration were recorded

cohols). A peak at 1710 cm⁻¹ (C=O) was observed in the starting material, which disappeared in the products. A broad band at 3570–3200 cm⁻¹ due to O–H (stretching) was seen in products, which suggests that product is a pinacolone.

Note

Experimental

Benzil salicylaldehyde mercury KCl and CH_3COONa were of AnalaR grade. The $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and H_2O used were double-distilled.

Cyclic voltammetric studies were carried out using a three-electrode cell assembly having glassy carbon as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode and platinum wire as the counter electrode. An Elico CL-95 potentiostat-cum-galvanostat coupled with a sweep generator and X-Y recorder was used for recording the polarization curves and for carrying out controlled potential electrolysis.

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